

Effectiveness of EMI Usage for Underachieving EFL Learners at a Turkish High-School

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Abstract

Using English as the medium of class instruction (EMI) is a widely acknowledged phenomenon and it is supported by many studies. Most of learners and schools agree upon the advantages of this practice and a high percentage of graduates of these educational institutes make use of it when they start their professional career. However, there is an ignored point of view by these people and decision makers; EMI is an unfair challenge for underachieving learners who have difficulties in comprehending instructions even in their first language, even in English as foreign language (EFL) classrooms, especially when it is not structured accordingly. This research features a mixed-method with a questionnaire, an interview and also analyses students' exam results comparing pre-and-post exam results. It aims to investigate the effectiveness of this EMI practice and tries to see it through underachieving learners' eyes in a Turkish high school, EFL classroom context. The findings intend to bring forward a new perspective for those who are in control of educational practices.

Key words: English-medium instruction, EFL, Mainstream Education, Underachieving learners

Introduction

Global education is a dynamic world and English-Medium Instruction (EMI) has been one of the trends in this landscape. What should never be forgotten is that EMI comes with both promises and challenges. As institutions all around the world increasingly implement EMI as a medium of instruction, the complex implications of this practice come front, starting debates and investigations into its effectiveness. This introduction comprises insights from multiple articles to dig into the key dimensions of EMI, exploring its challenges and the complex interplay of factors influencing its success.

The benefits of EMI, as articulated in the literature, extend beyond the borders of individual student experiences to encompass broader educational and institutional advantages (Elkhayma, 2022). English for instructional purposes in non-English speaking countries is seen as an opportunity to improve English proficiency, globalize content, and enhance critical thinking. Additionally, EMI is viewed as a strategic move for institutions to compete globally, attract international students, and enhance their research profiles. However, within these benefits, challenges such as inadequate English language proficiency among students and instructors, as well as threats to local languages and identity, are acknowledged.

Amid the surge of EMI adoption globally, examination of the methodologies employed for its implementation becomes imperative (Macaro, 2015). The effectiveness of various approaches, such as transitional programs or intensive support during EMI years, stands as a central question. Moreover, concerns about equity and access arise with the potential emergence of an elite form of education based on the ability to pay for private English language tutoring. As institutions navigate these implementation challenges, the need for quality research involving all stakeholders becomes evident.

Language challenges come large into the realm of EMI, with a particular focus on English for Academic Purposes (EAP) (Kohnke & Jarvis, 2023). In Hong Kong, academic writing poses a significant barrier for EAP learners, compounded by difficulties in discipline-specific vocabulary and understanding academic terms. Similar challenges manifest in speaking skills, with students struggling to articulate themselves fluently and engage effectively in discussions. These language challenges extend to study skills, impacting students' ability to plan, revise, and manage their time effectively. The intricate connection between language proficiency and academic success underscores the importance of addressing these challenges to optimize the EMI experience.

Beyond linguistic intricacies, the challenges of applying EMI extend to various dimensions, encompassing lecturers' language abilities, students' learning styles, and pedagogical issues (Ratna, 2017). Taiwanese students, for instance, express difficulties in understanding course content, inhibiting smooth expression and hindering discussion and interaction in the classroom. Zooming in on the speaking aspect of EMI, students' performance is influenced by factors such as motivation, confidence, anxiety, and listening ability. The nuances of these challenges emphasize the need for a nuanced understanding of the factors affecting students' performance in EMI environments.

Turkey, as a case study, presents a mixed landscape of criticisms and potential benefits associated with EMI (Ozer, 2020). Critics argue that the delivery of course content in EMI is ineffective, with content lecturers lacking improvisation and spontaneity. Despite these critiques, students' beliefs in the instrumental advantages of EMI persist, such as enhanced

employment prospects. This contradiction illustrates the complex perceptions surrounding EMI, where the practical shortcomings are weighed against perceived long-term benefits.

The language challenges faced by students in EMI are multifaceted, extending beyond vocabulary knowledge to encompass writing, speaking, note-taking, and comprehension (Kamasak&Sahan, 2023). These challenges underscore the need for a holistic approach to address various aspects of language proficiency and communication skills in EMI settings. Students' opinions about the effectiveness of EMI further contribute to the nuanced understanding of this instructional approach. The divergent perspectives underscore the complex interplay of factors influencing students' perceptions and experiences in EMI classrooms.

Transitioning into EMI presents an array of challenges for students, notably language-related hurdles in listening, writing, speaking, and reading (Aizawa, 2024). These challenges are intertwined with broader academic obstacles related to grasping concepts, adjusting to educational cultures, and navigating institutional conventions. The multifaceted nature of these challenges necessitates an exploration of the interplay between English proficiency, prior EMI experience, and academic success over time. This dynamic perspective acknowledges the evolving nature of students' experiences as they navigate the complexities of EMI.

Language barriers in education contribute significantly to educational inequality (Alhamami, 2023). These barriers can lead to unjust treatment, inaccurate assessment of student performance, and exclusion from class activities. The debate around the requirement for English fluency as a prerequisite for college admission raises questions about fairness and equality in education. The potential consequences of language policy on students' learning experiences highlight the complex relationship between language rights and human rights.

In conclusion, the landscape of EMI is a complex ground marked by promises and challenges, ranging from linguistic intricacies to broader institutional and societal implications. As institutions strive to harness the benefits of EMI, a nuanced understanding of the multifaceted challenges and opportunities is crucial. In the light of all these studies and the findings mentioned above, it is a critical need to run studies questioning its effectiveness in different learning environments with different learner groups. Therefore, this study tries to investigate effectiveness of EMI on underachieving Turkish EFL High school students' school subject achievement and whether it improves students' overall English performance.

Literature Review

Writing skills in English are the skills including the capacity of articulating clear and coherent thoughts in written form. Flower and Hayes (1981) states that writing is a cognitive process including stages of planning, translation of the ideas into text, reviewing and revising, and editing.

Reading skills in English are about the competency of an individual in comprehending and interpreting a written text. Grabe (2008) describes reading skills as a cognitive and linguistic process and states they involve decoding a written transcript, building meaning over it, and creating associates between it and existing knowledge.

Speaking skills in English involve being able to take part in interactive communication and express thought orally. Brown and Yule (1983) state that speaking skills include articulating

clear utterances, being part of an interaction, and altering the language according to different contexts.

Listening skills in English are the ones related to the ability of comprehending spoken language. Rost (2015) describes listening skills as the capacity of processing spoken language simultaneously that also includes recognition of sounds, words, and patterns.

Research Questions

RQ.1 Does using EMI have any positive effect on underachieving Turkish EFL students' school subject achievement?

RQ.2 Does EMI improve underachieving learners' overall English performance?

RQ.3 What are the students' perceptions about academic skills challenges in EMI?

Methodology

Participants and Setting

This study collected data from students using an online questionnaire to examine whether students' language difficulties, thoughts about EMI, language proficiency affect students' academic success in EMI. 14 students from a private high school in Istanbul answered the questions in the questionnaire. They listed their latest English test scores. Those 14 questionnaires were analysed.

The participants were high school students who were studying a high school preparatory program and those students were studying Math in EMI. Considering gender, 85,7% of the students were female, 14,3% of the students were male. All students were Turkish students and they all listed Turkish as their first language. Beside this, 28,6% of the students listed 3 other languages (Bosnian, Arabic, Bulgarian) as their second native languages that make them bilinguals. 28,6% of the students mentioned that they had had EMI experience before they started studying in preparatory program while 71,4% of them defined themselves as no-EMI-experienced students. The participants were the students who could not achieve the target score that had been decided by the school's ELT department to pass in the preparatory exemption test. The participant demographics are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Participant demographics (n=14)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	10	71.4
	Male	4	28.5
Level of education	High School	14	100
Year of study	High School Preparatory Program	14	100
L1 Background	Turkish	11	78.5
	Turkish and another	3	21.4
School subjects studied in EMI before high school	Yes	10	71.4
	No	4	28.6
Most recent English language test score	70 or more	3	21.4
	70 or fewer	11	78.5

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Data Collection Instrument

This study used an online questionnaire with 47 items in it to collect data; six of them asked for information about demography and one asked about student participants' the most recent English exam scores. The full questionnaire is available on the IRIS database (<https://www.iris-database.org/>) with the title 'The scale of student challenges in EMI education'.

The study used a seven-point Likert-type scale to record responses to the challenges that evaluate how participants define their experiences. There were also items related to participants' perceptions of the language related challenges they face in EMI classes and how they reflect on their performance. The study asked 4 semi-structured questions and 6 of students' answers were selected randomly. The study also features a comparison between the English and Math pre-and-post test scores of EMI group and the control groups that were 9th graders that studied Math in Turkish with the same curriculum provided by the school. The students in both groups were the students that failed in preparatory exemption test.

Data Collection and Analysis Procedure

The 7-point-likert questionnaire was shared with students via Google forms after a training session was held to inform them about the basic future and how to give their answers. The instructor also explained the terms that students were not familiar with. The internet connection support was also provided for the students that had problems. After the completion of the survey, the answers were analysed using the charts and details provided automatically by Google forms. The pre-and-post test data for English and Math scores for both experimental and control groups were collected from Turkish Ministry of education approved exams that were held during first education season of 2023-2024. All the students in the list of control groups are the ones that failed in English preparatory program exemption test but did not prefer studying the program.

Results and Findings

According the results of the questionnaire measuring student challenges in EMI education, students have a positive attitude towards the use of EMI in different school subjects. The overall results of the scale revealed that students found EMI practice somewhat easy in general (Table 2). The students mentioned about listening as the least challenging academic skill (5,09 on average) in EMI classes while they listed speaking as the most challenging one (4,36 on average).

Table 2. Student-reported student academic skills challenges in EMI results (1= very hard 7= very easy)

	Writing	Reading	Speaking	Listening
S1	4,93	4,56	3,10	4,67
S2	4,36	4,89	3,80	4,67

S3	5,64	5,44	5,10	5,00
S4	3,64	4,11	4,60	3,78
S5	4,71	5,33	4,30	6,33
S6	4,71	5,33	4,80	4,33
S7	3,64	4,33	3,70	4,89
S8	4,93	5,22	3,70	5,44
S9	5,43	4,56	4,40	4,78
S10	5,00	6,11	3,70	6,00
S11	4,86	4,89	4,70	5,56
S12	3,57	4,44	4,00	4,67
S13	5,43	6,33	6,10	5,89
S14	5,21	4,89	5,00	5,00
Average	4,72	5,03	4,36	5,09

Students somewhat agreed upon that they performed well and they were successful about learning academic content (Figure 1&2). 42% of the students stated that they somewhat agreed that they performed well in EMI courses (5,07 on average) and 6 of the students declared that they somewhat agreed with that their academic content learning through EMI was successful (5,28 on average).

Figure 1

Students' Answers about Their Performance in EMI Courses

Figure 2

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Students' Answers about Their Academic Content Learning in EMI Courses

My learning of academic content through my EMI courses is successful.

Students typed answers to semi-structured interview questions right after the application of the questionnaire. Two questions were asked to students about their feelings on the effectiveness of the use of EMI, whether they wanted to study other school subjects using EMI. There were also a question asking about their thoughts on the reason of a possible unsuccess. 10 out of 14 students gave positive questions about the effectiveness of EMI. These answers include words like “good”, “funny”, “Awesome!”. 8 students declared that they wanted to study other school subjects in English in following years while 4 of them are reluctant about it. Only one of the students strongly expressed it by saying “definitely no”. For the question about possible failure in EMI, the students did not give any common answers. Some of the reasons stated by students were lack of their effort, not understanding the material, lack of comprehension in English.

Pre-and-post test procedure showed that there was no significant variation in experimental groups’ English pre-and-post exam scores. There was slight decrease (-1,27%) in their English exam score average which means EMI brought no advantage for them in terms of English Language development. Moreover, their Math exam scores dropped by 38,52% on average. Almost all of the students acquired lower scores in comparison to their first exam scores. Only one student kept the exam score the same. Meanwhile, the control groups that followed the same Math curriculum in Turkish increased their English scores by 17,22% and 5,35% on average and Math scores by 9,52% and 7,59% on average. The study does not include students’ exam score in details due to possible ethical issues that might arise.

Discussion

Educational organizations have a tendency in trying to implement different teaching practices that are highly demanding on account of the reputation comes with. However, those practises occasionally fail to function as a result of not meeting requirements and English-medium instruction is one of them. Aizawa and Rose (2019) states that decision makers should consider things like language of instruction, sufficiently trained teachers, support provision and so on. Otherwise, it might result in discrepancies in practise. In our case, it is

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possible to see that control groups performed better in both school subjects; Math and English when we compare them to experimental group that comprises of motivated students in EMI practise. The students in the study group were the ones that failed in the exemption test and started studying preparation program for the sake of improving English language competency. Although they had a positive attitude towards studying in EMI, this did not help them much in terms of getting better grades.

Another important point to be mentioned is their background knowledge of the students in the field they experience EMI. Dimova (2020) underlines the importance of the background knowledge of the content beside language proficiency. Assessing learners' readiness in different perspectives in advance could lead to be successful in achieving program goals while ignoring it may possible failure.

All in all, under these circumstances, the failure is more probable consequence than success in EMI practise.

Conclusions

The aim of the study was to examine the effectiveness of the use EMI for underachieving EFL learners. In the light of the findings, it is possible to conclude that EMI is an application that demands a lot of preparedness by the institution such as teacher training programs, preliminary exams, specifically designed materials. When the organizations lack those preparation, effectiveness of the practise fades away and it causes disadvantages for the students rather than yielding gain. In conclusion, practises like EMI should be planned, designed and executed carefully to maximize, or optimize, its gaining.

Limitations of the Study

This study uses data from a limited number of students from a private high school in a specific district in Istanbul. This might avoid generalizing the results and finding. Cultural differences, different governmental policies and other variables might give different result in different settings.

Implications for Further Research

Further research could be held using higher number of students from different school in different districts. This might provide a better insight about strengths and weaknesses of EMI practise under different circumstances.

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